

Absence of fever with infection in an elderly female with diagnostic dilemma :A Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Fever is a common manifestation of an infectious disorder leading to prompt diagnosis and treatment. Sometimes, infections may present with atypical manifestations without fever, particularly in elderly and immunocompromised patients posing diagnostic challenges and delay in treatment. The case discussed here describes an elderly patient with comorbidities presenting with recurrent episodes of vomiting without any definite pointers in diagnosis. Proper history and clinical examination with investigations lead to the diagnosis of emphysematous pyelitis which is a life threatening disorder occurring in immunosuppressed patients causing morbidity and mortality. The importance lies in the timely diagnosis and intervention with appropriate intravenous antibiotics and other measures reducing morbidity and mortality.

Keywords: Emphysematous pyelitis.

INTRODUCTION

Case Report

A 60 years old diabetic, hypertensive female, housewife presented with recurrent episodes of vomiting without any fever, headache, loss of consciousness, weakness of any side of the body for the last 5 days. There was no history of trauma, pain abdomen, bladder bowel complaint, ear discharge or visual impairment. The patient was on metformin for diabetes mellitus and on amlodipine for hypertension. On examination, patient was conscious, but drowsy. There was tachypnoea with blood pressure of 140/90 mm of hg and tachycardia was present. There was mild pallor,

On examination of the Gastrointestinal system, there was no tenderness in any quadrant of the abdomen, particularly the gall bladder point, McBurney's point. Renal angle was also non tender. There was no organomegaly, Intestinal peristaltic sounds were normal, Temperature was normal.

On examination of the CNS, neck was supple without any lateralization. Examination of other systems were unremarkable.

A provisional diagnosis of acute gastritis was made and patient was put on nasogastric tube, catheterization was done, intravenous PPI, Ondansetron, IV fluid NS and RL was started and investigations sent were CBC, FBS, urea, creatinine, electrolytes. ECG, Chest X ray were done with USG Whole abdomen. Urine was sent for routine and microscopic examination with peripheral blood smear and procalcitonin.

There was neutrophilic leukocytosis (TLC-12,100/MM³) with haemoglobin of 10.2 gm/dl. Urea was 34 mg/dl with creatinine of 1.5 mg/dl denoting pre renal AKI. Sodium was 130 mmol/l with serum potassium 2.9 mmol/l. LFT, Amylase and lipase were normal. USG WA revealed bulky left kidney with increased left echogenicity with possibility of some calculi in midpole and CECT KUB was advised which was not done due to increased creatinine levels. Urine CS revealed Escherichia coli with colony

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count of 10^5 CFU/ml sensitive to Meropenem. When urine RE revealed plenty of pus cells on day 2 of admission, injection cefotaxime was started empirically which was changed to injection Meropenem on receiving the urine CS report.

With fluid therapy and potassium supplementation, AKI resolved, patient started to improve on day 5 of admission, nasogastric tube was removed and patient started oral feeding. Vomiting decreased subsequently with normalization of electrolytes and CECT WA was done instead of CECT KUB to detect any additional abdominal pathology which revealed emphysematous cystitis, left sided emphysematous pyelitis with urethritis, diffuse circumferential mild bowel wall thickening (?reactive changes) (Fig 1). In right kidney, perinephric fat stranding was there and left kidney revealed perinephric fat stranding with multiple air foci in left pelvicalyceal system. Few air foci were present in the left ureteric lumen. Multiple air foci were noted in urinary bladder wall, both intramural and intra luminal. No hydronephrosis, calculi were noted.

CT Brain plain, EEG revealed no abnormality and hyponatremia work up revealed normal thyroid profile, 8 am serum cortisol levels, ACTH. The patient was referred to Urology and URS with DJ stenting was advised by the Urologist. The patient was symptom free on day 10 of admission and was discharged on day 16 of admission with 12 days of meropenem dosage and advised follow up to Urology and General Medicine OPD.

DISCUSSION

Emphysematous pyelonephritis (EPN) is a severe necrotizing infection of the upper urinary tract with involvement of the renal parenchyma and sometimes the peri renal kidney tissues. There is formation of gas in the kidney parenchyma, collecting system, perinephric tissue. Diabetic patients have a high mortality from 40-90%. Emphysematous pyelitis (EP) with renal pelvic gas and emphysematous cystitis (EC) with gas in the wall and lumen of the bladder may occur independently of associated EPN.

Diabetes mellitus is the most common risk factor¹ with high mortality rates². A close differential is acute pyelonephritis. Intravenous antibiotics and percutaneous drainage may be needed.³ *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella* are the commonest organisms with *Proteus*, *Enterococcus*, *Aspergillus*, *Clostridium* being also implicated and rarely *Candida* are associated. Polymicrobial affections may occur.^{3,4,5,6} Risk factors are diabetes mellitus, obstruction in urinary tract and hypertension.^{1,7,8} Previous urological interventions, hospitalization and antibiotics are not associated.

Patients with confusion, old age, AKI, thrombocytopenia, hypoalbuminemia, severe proteinuria have bad outcomes. Asia reports increased number of cases.⁹ Poorly controlled diabetes causes propagation of bacteria and progression of disease because of high tissue glucose, decreased supply of oxygen to the tissues and microvascular damage.⁷ Accumulation of gas occurs due to microbes fermenting glucose and lactate with production of carbon dioxide, hydrogen and nitrogen¹⁰. Fever, nausea, vomiting and chills are common and pain abdomen, renal angle tenderness, pneturia, palpable crepitations are signs.^{11,12} CT imaging has 100% sensitivity followed by USGWA and X RAY KUB (69% and 65% respectively). EPN classification is by 3 methods such as Michaeli et al classification, Wan et al classification and Huang and Tseng classification.^{13,14,10}

Antibiotics

Keeping in mind the common pathogens, single antibiotic regimens include 3rd or 4th generation cephalosporins or carbapenems for reduction of gram negative sepsis mortality. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Enterococcus* should also be covered. Fluoroquinolone resistance is high¹⁵. alternative combination is amikacin and 3rd generation cephalosporin due to low levels of resistance. Standard duration is a 2 weeks course and response is guided by improvement of clinical symptoms.

The patient discussed here had none of the classical symptoms, had diabetes and hypertension with confusion, AKI which are all poor prognostic factors. But prompt diagnosis, aggressive

hyperglycemia therapy with insulin, anti hypertensive treatment and most importantly appropriate antibiotic administration and proper duration of therapy lead to

resolution of symptoms ,glycemia control and repeat negative urine culture¹⁶.

Figure 1: Emphysematous cystitis and left sided pyelitis

CONCLUSION

Emphysematous pyelitis/pyelonephritis presents with systemic symptoms with morbidity and mortality. Old age and immunosuppression may mask fever and other symptoms causing delay in diagnosis and treatment. Clinicians should be very alert to detect the subtle signs and symptoms ,address the poor prognostic factors,timely parenteral appropriate antibiotic administration and Urology referral to avoid complications.

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